

FIRE STRUCTURAL PERFORMANCE OF FLAX FIBRE REINFORCED LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Eco-friendly flax fibres are increasingly being used in polymer matrix composites because they possess specific mechanical properties comparable to fibreglass composites while being cheap, less energy intensive to produce and more bio-sustainable. Flax fibre composites are being considered for applications where fire is a risk (e.g. buildings) and therefore an understanding of their high temperature and fire resistant properties is important. The fire structural performance of a flax reinforced polymer matrix composite is experimentally assessed in this paper. Fire structural testing revealed that exposure of a flax fibre reinforced vinyl ester composite to a radiant heat flux caused rapid weakening and failure under tensile loading. Elevated temperature tensile tests on flax fibre tows indicate that the poor fire resistance is due in part to fibre softening due to the low glass transition temperatures of hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin. In addition, micro-cracks are formed in flax fibres exposed to moderate temperatures, which contributes to the low fire resistance of the composite. The results indicate the exposure to fires with radiant temperatures as low as ~100°C will result in significant structural weakening and cause rapid failure.

Keywords: Fire, Flax fibres, Natural fibre composite

1 INTRODUCTION

Plant-derived lignocellulosic fibres have emerged as a viable substitute for more expensive and non-renewable synthetic fibres used to reinforce polymer matrix composites. Flax (*Linum usitatissimum*) is one of the most widely used natural fibres in composites due to its moderate cost, biodegradability and low environmental impact along with low density and good specific mechanical properties [1, 2]. Table 1 compares the physical and mechanical properties of E-glass against flax fibres, which are being used as a substitute. Although not as stiff and strong as glass fibre, flax has higher specific stiffness and similar specific strength. Furthermore, the mechanical properties of flax fibre are improving due to better manufacturing and handling techniques and surface treatments [3-5]. As the properties of flax fibre composites continue to improve their use in semi-structural applications such as buildings and decking will grow. With the selection of materials becoming increasingly influenced by their inherent environmental impact and sustainability, the use of eco-friendly natural fibres is emerging as a potential alternative to glass fibres in composites [6].

The physical and mechanical properties of natural fibres and their composites have been widely studied [1-3, 7-12], although little is known about their fire structural resistance [6, 13-15]. The susceptibility of polymer matrix composites to fire can be a key issue restricting their use [16]. Load-bearing composite structures can soften, deform and eventually fail when exposed to fire. Also, the release of toxic smoke and heat adds to the fire hazard. Given that fire is a critical design factor in

building and many other structural applications, it is important to understand the fire structural resistance of natural fibre composites that may potentially be used in load-bearing structures.

While it is expected that natural fibre composites will be inferior to glass and other synthetic fibre composites, just how bad their fire resistance is remains unknown. Plant based fibres start to weaken at temperatures as low as 105°C [17] although decomposition of the organic constituents which provide stiffness and strength (e.g. hemicellulose, cellulose, lignin) does not occur until much higher temperatures.

This paper investigates the fire structural resistance of a flax fibre reinforced polymer matrix composite. The effect of the applied tensile stress on the survivability of the flax fibre composite is determined. The paper also aims to determine the mechanisms responsible for the weakening of flax fibre composites exposed to fire.

Property	E-Glass [18]	Flax Fibres [19]
Diameter (μm)	8-14	10-80
Density (g/cm^3)	2.56	1.4
Young's modulus (GPa)	76	50-70
Tensile strength (GPa)	1.4-2.5	0.5-1.5
Elongation to failure (%)	1.8-3.2	2-3
Specific Young's Modulus ($\text{GPa per g}/\text{cm}^3$)	30	36-50
Specific tensile strength ($\text{GPa per g}/\text{cm}^3$)	0.5-1	0.4-1.1

Table 1: E-glass fibre and flax fibre properties

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

A composite was made using unidirectional flax fabric (Lineo FlaxTape©, 150 g/m^2) and vinyl ester resin (SPV 1265, Nuplex Composites). The flax fabric was stacked in a cross-ply pattern, and then infused with vinyl ester using the vacuum bag resin infusion (VBRI) process. Following infusion, the composite was cured under ambient conditions (23°C, 55% RH). The glass transition temperature of the composite was 90°C and the fibre volume content was 40% (determined using ASTM D-3171).

2.1 High temperature testing of flax tows

The tensile strength of flax fibre tows was measured at room and elevated temperature (25 - 275°C) using the test method illustrated in figure 1. The tow ends were wrapped around large-diameter circular rollers to gradually introduce the applied tensile force into the gauge section of the sample via friction. A 10 mm section of the tow was heated using a hot air gun fitted with a variable temperature controller. The tow temperature was measured using a thermocouple lightly touching the sample. Once the tow had reached and maintained the test temperature for five minutes (to ensure all the fibres were at the same temperature), it was loaded to failure at an extension rate of 2 mm/min. Five tows were tested at the each temperature to measure the average value and determine the scatter in the failure loads.

Figure 1: Schematic for flax fibre tow tests using a hot are gun

2.2 Mechanical testing of composites

The tensile stiffness and strength properties of the flax composite were measured between 20 and 200°C. The tests were performed according to ASTM D3039 with a sample gauge length of 150 mm, width of 25 mm and thickness of 4 mm. The tensile tests were performed at a loading rate of 2 mm/min inside a temperature controlled hot box attached to a 50 kN Instron machine.

2.3 Fire structural testing of composites

Small-scale fire structural tests were performed on the flax fibre composite to assess its fire resistance. A schematic illustration of the test is presented in Figure 2. The test involves loading the composite in tension while simultaneously heating one side using a 5000W cone-shaped radiant heater. Composite specimens were loaded at between 20 and 80% of the room temperature strength using a 250 kN MTS machine while one surface was exposed to a constant radiant heat flux. The distance between the heater and the composite specimen was set at 25 mm. The specimens were 600 mm long, 50 mm wide and ~9 mm thick. The tensile force and heat flux were applied to the composite until it failed.

Figure 2: Fire structural test setup

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Structural performance of flax composite in fire

The fire resistance of the flax-vinyl ester composite when exposed to a simulated fire attack under tensile loading was determined experimentally by performing fire structural tests at the radiant heat flux of 10 and 35 kW/m². Figure 3 shows the temperature rise measured at the front surface, middle and back surface of the composite with increasing exposure time to the heat fluxes. The front face, which was directly exposed to the heat flux, heated up rapidly and reached a maximum temperature of ~280°C at 10 kW/m² and 600°C at 35 kW/m². As expected, the heating rates at the middle and back surface were slower due to the low through-thickness thermal conductivity of the composite.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Measured temperature-time curves for the flax composite at (a) 10 kW/m² and (b) 35 kW/m². x defines the distance below the heated surface of the composite.

Figure 4 shows the effect of applied tensile stress on the failure times of the flax composite when exposed to the heat fluxes. As expected, the failure time increased when the applied stress was reduced, although even at the lowest stress the composite only survived for less than 10 minutes at 10 kW/m² and 5 minutes at 35 kW/m². The results indicate that the fire structural performance of flax composites is greatly inferior to carbon and glass fibre composites, which require much higher stresses and heat fluxes to fail [20, 21].

Figure 4: Effect of constant tensile stress on the failure time of the flax composite when exposed to heat fluxes of 10 and 35 kW/m²

The mechanisms controlling for the poor fire resistance were investigated by elevated tensile tests on the flax fibrous tows. Figure 5 shows the effect of increasing temperature on the percentage losses to the stiffness and failure load of the unidirectional flax tows. The glass transition temperatures of the lignin and cellulose are indicated in the figure.

The tow strength decreased at a linear rate with increasing temperature and the flax had lost virtually all strength by ~275°C, which is about the maximum surface temperature in the fire structural tests at 10 kW/m². The stiffness decreased slightly up to ~125°C and then remained constant up to the highest test temperature.

Flax fibres are made up of composite layers reinforced by cellulose fibrils, which are grouped in bundles to form mesofibrils. The fibril orientation plays an important role in the tensile properties of flax fibres [22]. The cellulose mesofibrils are embedded in an amorphous polysaccharide matrix composed mainly of pectins and hemicellulose [17]. At room temperature, flax fibres contain ~4-6 wt. % of water which acts as a cell wall plasticizer [23]. At temperatures above ~100°C, evaporation of water contributes to the loss in tensile strength. The extraction of water embrittles the constituents within the fibre, especially the hydrated gel network formed by the polysaccharides [24], which in turn affects the interactions between mesofibrils and the pectin matrix. The lignin and cellulose undergo a glass-to-rubbery transition at temperatures of about 135°C and 175°C, respectively, which contributes to the loss in tensile strength. In addition, the flax fibres were physically damaged when exposed to high temperature. Flax fibres contain naturally-occurring surface and internal flaws, and these grew in size and density during exposure to high temperature. Figure 6 shows flax fibres before and after exposure to high temperature (250°C for 5 minutes), and longitudinal cracks developed along the fibres at high temperature. During fire structural testing the composite was rapidly heated to the temperatures required to cause significant softening and weakening of the flax fibres, and this would account in part for the poor fire structural resistance.

Figure 5: Effect of increasing temperature on failure load and stiffness of flax tows

Figure 6: SEM images of flax tows (a) at room temperature and (b) thermally treated at 250°C

The softening behaviour of the flax composite was investigated further by elevated temperature tensile tests. The effect of increasing temperature on the tensile stiffness and strength is shown in figure 7. The properties decreased rapidly with increasing temperature, and this was due to the combined effects of glass transition softening of the polymer matrix ($T_g = 120^\circ\text{C}$), the loss of stress transfer efficiency between the fibres due to matrix softening, and weakening of the fibres themselves. The composite lost virtually all of its tensile stiffness and strength by 200°C, which accounts for its poor fire structural resistance.

Figure 7: Effect of temperature on tensile strength and stiffness of flax-vinylester composite

Thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed on the flax fibres, vinyl ester resin and the flax-vinyl ester composite to determine whether these materials decomposed significantly during fire structural testing, which may contribute to the poor fire resistance. The TGA was performed in an inert atmosphere (nitrogen) at the heating rate of 10°C/min up to 600°C using a Perkin Elmer TGA-7 instrument.

The TGA curves are shown in Figure 8, and the flax fibres initially lose a small amount of mass (~4-6%) above ~50-100°C due to the evaporation of water and possibly other low vapour pressure compounds. Lignin decomposes via chain scission reactions over the temperature range of ~160-400°C, and this accounts in part for the measured mass loss [13]. Degradation of polysaccharides occurs between 250-400°C [11]. Cellulose and hemicellulose within wood fibres start to degrade at ~300°C, and this accounts for the rapid mass loss of the flax above this temperature shown in the TGA curve [25]. The decomposition reaction processes of cellulose, hemicellulose and other constituents of the fibrils results in the formation of flammable hydrocarbon volatiles, non-combustible gases (mostly water), tars, and some char [13]. The onset of decomposition for the vinyl ester resin occurs at ~350°C which reveals it is more chemically stable to higher temperatures than the fibres, indicating that flax as reinforcement had a detrimental effect on the thermal stability of the composite.

Figure 8: TGA mass loss curves for flax fibres, neat vinylester resin and flax-vinylester composite

4 CONCLUSION

There is growing interest in the use of flax fibres as the reinforcement for polymer matrix composites due to their biodegradability, low cost, and good specific mechanical properties. Flax fibre composite studied here displayed poor fire structural performance due to weakening of both the flax fibres and polymer matrix. The fibres weakened via a complex series of physical and chemical processes, including water evaporation, glass transition softening followed by decomposition of the lignin, cellulose, hemicellulose and other organic compounds which provide stiffness and strength, as well as damage (cracking). Glass transition softening of the polymer matrix and the resultant loss in stress transfer efficiency between the flax fibres contributed to structural weakening of the composite in fire, although matrix decomposition had no influence due to the low failure temperatures. The temperatures and stress levels at which the flax fibre composite failed during simulated fire exposure are much lower than for glass and carbon fibre composites [20, 21, 26], which demonstrates the poor fire resistance of the material. Therefore, it is important to increase the fire structural safety of flax and other plant-based fibre composites by various surface treatments and coatings.

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